

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES,
SRINIVAS NAGAR, MUKKA, SURATHKAL,
MANGALORE- 574146**

VALUE ADDED COURSE

ON

Lactation Management

DEPARTMENT OF CHILD HEALTH NURSING

Name of the course:Lactation Management

Aim of the Course:

The aim of the course is develop in-depth knowledge and understanding in lactation management. It also help the students to develop competency in providing quality care to the lactating women and her families

Objectives of the Course

On completion of the module, the student will be able to

1. understand the concept of lactation and anatomy of breast in postpartum women.
2. discuss the physiology of lactation and composition of breast milk.
3. develop competencies in providing quality nursing care to these women based on nursing process.
4. educate women and families about the lactation problems faced by them and improve in breast feeding.
5. discuss the advantages of breast feeding and bonding.
6. explain the importance of taking well balanced diet to facilitate lactation.

Duration:

Theory: 30 hours

Practical: 20 hours

Evaluation :

Assessment methods:

- Test paper (Objective test, short answers and case scenario and questions) - 30 marks
- Assessment of assignments/skills - 20 mark

The examination will be conducted by the Institute of Nursing Sciences affiliated to Srinivas University

Criteria for eligibility to appear for University Exam

- i. 80% attendance in theory
- ii. 100% attendance in practical

Criteria for pass

In order to pass a candidate should obtain at least 50% marks aggregate including internal Assessment and marks obtained from college examination

Award of Certificate/Diploma

Certificate will be awarded by the Institute of Nursing Sciences affiliated to Srinivas University.

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Abhirami Joseph

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
on "Lactation Management" from 01/02/2022 to 01/07/2022

A handwritten signature in blue ink, likely belonging to the Course Coordinator.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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Course Coordinator

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III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Aksa M Jose

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Aleena A

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Anagha K Anil

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
on "Lactation Management" from 01/02/2022 to 01/07/2022

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Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Anagha Pj

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms Angel Maria

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms Arya Vk

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III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms Gopika Av

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms Greety Francis

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Hridya K.S

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Irfanfayis C.N

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Jomol M

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms Josini Joseph

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Kavya Suresh

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'S. Suresh'.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Liya V.C

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms Nafihasulthana V

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms Nimisha Jenson

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Rajinrajan M.V

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Rima John

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'R. John', written over a white rectangular background.

Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Rojan R

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'Rojan R', written over a white rectangular background.

Course Coordinator

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Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Sandra Elizebethrintu

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Shahana C.M

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Sheethaldhanaraj K.T

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Shruthi.K.G

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Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Sivapriya M

III Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed value added course
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Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Sneha Judy T.J

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A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'Sona L.A.', written over a white rectangular background.

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